

Corporate Social Responsibility of Inland Resort Owners and Community Attitude of Barangay Residents towards Local Tourism Industry

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Abstract: The study was undertaken to describe the level of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) of inland resort owners towards the community attitude of barangay residents in Toril. The study used the non-experimental quantitative research design, employing descriptive-correlation technique. The data were gathered from 320 barangay residents in eight different inland resort destinations around Toril and using a downloaded questionnaire and through purposive sampling technique. The result showed that the level of Corporate Social Responsibility of Inland resort owners was high which indicated that the items relating to the CSR were often manifested. In addition result showed that the level of Community Attitude of barangay residents was high which indicated that the items relating to the community attitude were often manifested. Further, data showed that there was a significant relationship between the corporate social responsibility of inland resort owners and community attitude of barangay residents and that the overall corporate social responsibility practices of inland resort owners significantly influenced community attitude. Among the domains of corporate social responsibility, social practices significantly influenced community attitude. Likewise, between the two domains, the social practices in its singular capacity is the best predictor of community attitude

Keywords: *business administration, corporate social responsibility, community attitude, inland resort, Philippines*

I. Introduction

The positive support of the community is very important so good connection in doing business in a local setting. Most of the studies suggest that there is no possible of tourism sustainability in a location that does not supported by the community, according to the study of Twining-Ward and Butler (2002) and Ahn, Lee and Shafer (2002). Therefore, seeing the disposition of the community and their recognitions would frame in regards to tourism improvement might make important information for the individuals in the tourism business especially to territorial tourism advancement tasks. But it would be needless to the state that to elicit local support would entail something that would reciprocate the community from where investors have greatly benefited and thereby strike a balance. This is where an intentional trade-off has to be considered by those in the tourism industry for the local residents' support. It is in this respect that businesses have to value the significance of what/s normally referred as corporate social responsibility or CSR.

In the study of Cumming (2008), he defined the CSR as a matter of interest wherein the corporations voluntarily involve their organization in social responsibility practices and in their interactions with their stakeholders. In addition, Tamajón, and Aulet, (2013) explained that CSR could be better understood as a charitable involvement by the organization to improve the lives of the recipients of its philanthropic causes and consequently improve the company's corporate advantage. Moreover, there were already several studies conducted in the subject of CSR and that there are a lot of studies relating to CSR by some organization in hotel, restaurant and tourism industry, but there is still a small study relating the CSR in small businesses according to (Tamajón&Aulet, 2013).

It is on above context that the researcher decided to conduct the study of corporate social responsibility of inland resort owners and vis-à-vis the attitude of barangay residents with respect to tourism development. Indeed, there are existing studies about tourism development; however, the studies were likely about the CSR of the owners of the hospitality business. The domain of the CSR in this study focuses on three variables which are social practices, economic practices and environmental practices. This study can help future researcher and can aid in filling the space on scarcity of literature and related studies on the subject, especially in the local setting. Furthermore, this could be beneficial to the inland resort owners and to the local people in determining and implementing the important role of the local government and its policies with respect in developing local tourism development.

Research Objective

The research aimed to identify the domain of CSR that greatly influences community attitude on the residents in Toril. The specific objectives are as follows:

1. To describe the corporate social responsibility levels of tourism owners in their area in terms of:

- 1.1 social practices;
- 1.2 economic practices, and
- 1.3 environmental practices;

2.To assess the attitude levels of the community attitude on tourism development in their area in terms of:

- 2.1 tourism environmental impacts;
- 2.2 government management of tourism;
- 2.3 community satisfaction, and
- 2.4 sustainable tourism;

3.To determine the significant relationship of the corporate social responsibility (CSR) of inland resort owners to the attitudes of the residents in the community of Toril; and

4.To identify which domain of corporate social responsibility can best influence the community attitudes of barangay residents in Toril Davao City.

Hypothesis

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant relationship between the level of corporate social responsibility of inland resort owners and the level of community attitudes of barangay residents in Toril Davao City.

2. There is no specific domain of corporate social responsibility that can influence the community attitude of the barangay residents of Toril.

Review of Related Literature

Presented in this section are the related literature and studies that have bearings to the present study. The independent variable is Corporate Social Responsibility with indicators consisting of Social practices, Economic practices and Environmental practices. This was taken from the study of Tamajón and iAulet(2013) of International Centre for Research in Events, Tourism and Hospitality Leeds Metropolitan University.

The dependent variable is Community Attitude with indicators consisting of tourism environmental impacts; government management of tourism; community satisfaction, and sustainable tourism. This was taken from the study of Assante, Wen and Lottig (2012).

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)

The thought of CSR had marginal consideration to the world of organization but it is claimed that the current crisis has made it a greater priority (Franklin, 2008). This was in reference to an earlier study by Branco and Rodrigues (2006) which cited CSR can guide in making of assets and capacity that can have effect on the company's advantage. These opportunities were explained throughout the application of the Resource-Based View (RBV).

On other hand, pressures from stakeholders are manifested especially by the need for accountability starting with its customers, who increasingly denounce possible fraudulent green washing practices (Ramus & Montiel, 2005), and continues with other stakeholders (Sen & Bhattacharya, 2001).

There are numbers of tourism organizations that includes CSR in their business organization, among different issues such as: trying to develop the environment, help assist the residents' live and upgrade welfare on the workers. While there is progress, there are also concerns about green washing (Self, Self, & Bell-Haynes, 2010).

Although the literature on CSR in the sector is scarce, it has grown in recent years (Kang, Lee, & Huh, 2010). Some research has decided on reducing the cost and expenditure source in tourism sector (Ayuso, 2006). The main motivation is reduction of cost in order to have an organizational advantage (Knowles, Macmillan, Palmer, Grabowski & Hashimoto, 1999).

There are different meanings of the term CSR, all have concurred that the complete range that includes connecting the economical, societal and ecological presentation of the organization and its charitable extension (Bohdanowicz & Zientara, 2009). However, Font, Walmsley, Cogotti, McCombes and Häusler (2012) argued in this agreement too reflects the widely used standard in corporate social responsibility practices.

First indicator for corporate social responsibility is social practices. According to Pascariu (2011), social responsibility means the voluntary taking on by businesses of the social and environment objectives, in alignment with their economical idea, relating to the ecological aspect that partners to the stakeholders of the firms and with the external location who are the community.

In Europe, the idea additionally alludes to the moral aspects, recognition of the essential rights, responsibility of the sway of benefits of the business upon the culture as a whole, and also an animated part in accomplishing those vital destinations of the nearby community, toward regional, national level. Pascariu (2011) further added that CSR is a perception on the organization's practice in societal and ecological laws which involved actions over and above the regulatory or lawful responsibility of the organizations, by pleasing a social purpose.

A study by Porter and Kramer (2006) cited that organization could weigh several societal reasons which include educating the local, accessibility of health, availability of accommodation, social bias, etc. This issue can influence the companies to employ appropriate workforce from the locality as most societies depend on organization and so on. Organization gives merchandises, tax contribution and employment while community put away, give employment legislation (Iraqi, 2010). One can't survive without alternate. Therefore, it will be significant that organizations acknowledge their impact in the group keeping the place they work and that evolving their viewpoint something like the group keeping will prompt future profits for both over more routes over particular case.

The second indicator for CSR is economic practices. In the framework of De Grosbois (2012), referring to the World Business Council for Sustainable Development's (WBCSD) defines, CSR as a progressing obligation by the organization to act morally and add to economic development while recuperating the value of time of the labor force and their family members as well as the neighborhood and the people at large (WBCSD, 2000). However, this must be clearly stated that CSR involves three impacts of operations that is essential in developing a scheme that engaged the entire organization and process related in it (Coles, Fencolava & Dinan, 2013). The term CSR for in this study is described as an in progress growth in the organization that incorporates the three scopes.

CSR definition covers sustainable economic development, an idea that consigns to its financial aspect, working with the organization, which refers to its moral disposition. The inspiration of the organization in taking up social

responsibility is understood in a different way, whether the researchers are professionally inclined with ethical standard or economical aspect. In the assumption of researchers, relating to moral principle, organizations are usually to take up social responsibilities practices in doing right things to the community. In addition public accountability is the devotion of the organization in contributing to economical sustainability, operating together in workforce, the district and people to develop a good life (WBCSD, 2000).

In economics, CSR is viewed as tactical instrument to attain financial goals and eventually, profit maximization, where organizations are held accountable to its shareholders (Garriga&Mele, 2004). Clearly stated, the main motivation is increasing profit. Organizations apply CSR so that they can promote economic sustainability by forming a product that will improve marketing by conducting generally responsible attitude (Lantos, 1999).

An early face up to these vision was presented by Carroll (1979) who had a second thought of the definition of CSR, pointing out to the detail that organizations are considered to have accountability not only to their organization, but to the community as well (Quazi, 2003). Carroll (1979) obtained a conceptual model of CSR that was based on categories of social accountability which states that the leading social responsibility is economic.

The next indicator for corporate social responsibility is environmental practices. Hotels can prove commitment to environmental protection by managing environmental practices motivated by cost savings. By taking greening program that protects the energy and water consumption by reducing waste production in lodging establishments that can generate an important amount of wealth considering a lodging establishment usually had an expense of 4- 6% on revenue on energy, much even more for luxurious hotel generating 10% of energy revenue (National Grid, 2004).

Tourism, in itself is a field where the implementation of CSR policies is particularly important, since the success of every tourism business depends on the preservation of the place it is situated (Bader, 2005). The United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) and United Nation World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) (2005) reports have defined sustainable tourism as one that takes full account of its current and future economic, social and environmental impacts, addressing the needs of visitors, the industry, the environment, and the host communities. They significantly stressed that tourism businesses should not only focus on their present success, but also incorporate the future, as well as the needs of the various stakeholders and other parties as important (Brewi, 2013).

As has been observed, it is generally considered that companies tend to prioritize CSR measures that offer cost savings and resources in the short term or generate resources and capabilities (RBV), which in turn lead to competitive advantages leading to increased profits. CSR as equal to CFP (corporate financial performance) has been the „holy grail“ of the literature on CSR in recent years (Carroll &Shabana, 2010). However, the same literature has not been conclusive on this relationship, finding positive, neutral and negative associations (Griffin & Mahon, 1997) and has even been criticized by an excessive bias considering CSR only as a business case (Lee, 2008).

Some author suggested that perhaps a enhanced approach is not only looking for CSR input to economical presentation but its union with the society, obviously part of organizational approach (Porter

& Kramer, 2006). For authors like De Bakker, Groenewegen and Hond, (2005), the question should not be whether CSR has something to do with results but rather, as to the part of social responsibility, for what purpose it may serve, and the stakeholders it speaks to. Organizations are motivated by competitive advantage, it focuses on the reactions to the members of the company and those who are focused to respond on the success of the organization (employees, consumers, government, etc.), and finally selfless organization usually respond to concerns on a bigger and more freely distinct groups such as the ecology and the social.

In contrast to traditional assumptions about the barriers (lack of budget, time, capacity) to implement CSR (Jenkins, 2006), many small businesses seem to be very aware of the potential benefits of taking responsibility for being sustainable and understand it as a business model, especially by creating proactive relationships with stakeholders and generating reputation.

As the social capital accrued from their commitment is vital for their survival, CSR can be understood as a valid use of their limited resources (Sen, 2011). Other authors point at the importance of values, pragmatism and owners/managers routines as drivers (Murillo & Lozano, 2006).

Community Attitude

The study by Hanafiah, Jamaludin and Zulkifly (2013) cited the local community as main participants to growth of tourism. The study about attitude of community towards tourism development is numerously increasing. However, there are some limitations of the research on the personal benefits that the local community will support future tourism development. Jafari (2001) suggested that in the development of tourism, the roles of the local community must take into consideration towards their support on future tourism development by looking into their personal benefits or gain, the reaction on improvement on the destination and carry for expectations in tourism destination development.

Hanafiah, Jamaludin and Zulkifly (2013) added the support of this study in their research about community attitude in Tioman Island. According to their findings, residents in the island were only used to focus on agricultural activities until the late 80's wherein the island was evolved into a vast tourist destination of the country. In the year 2011, there were about an estimated 220,000 tourist arrivals, majority of which were local tourists. Their study was focused on the assessment of the community attitude towards tourism development taking into account some perceived personal benefits and the impacts as they help for tourism growth. They did so by assessing the attitude of the community in preparation for outlook in destination expansion with the support of the residents as part of the participating group in the administrative management process.

Telfer (2002) also explained on rampant development of tourism added a lot in tourism development. Community attitude towards tourism acknowledged some factors that "directly and indirectly" affect the community. Furthermore, the study by Telfer cited some major cultural and economic attributes that created the opportunity for the local communities. On the other hand, Hanafiah, Harun and Jamaludin (2013) cited that the community creates a link between the economic stability. This is due to the capability of the tourism development in generating proceeds as well as providing employment opportunities. Rapid growth in the tourism destination will definitely change the destination scene, but with spontaneous destination development, can take an effect to ecological dreadful conditions and economical discrepancy amongst the resident, they added. To assess the level of tourism development, Aref (2010) explained that a community can be any existing potential that shares common concerns, some interests and goals. Further studies by Etiosa (2012) added that the local community plays an important role to the members by promoting their physical, social, psychological and spiritual well-being.

Studying the local residents' thoughts, feelings, and attitudes is one way for this research to obtain information about tourism impacts. Since they are the directly-affected group and immediate participants of the development of tourism, residents are more sensitive to tourism's impacts and benefits. As such, they could make relatively proper assessments of the current issues facing tourism development. Moreover, the long-term and successful development of tourism is dependent on the local community's attitude towards tourism and tourists, and therefore it should be developed according to the host community's needs and desires (Andriotis, 2005), because the community attitude is essential for visitor satisfaction and repeat visitation (Sheldon & Abenoja, 2001).

In view to the destination development, researchers have been distinguished to provide important contribution to the welfare of the community, which is why organization should take into actions considering that their plans and actions should, reflects the upcoming programs to be provided in the community (Lankford, 2001).

Furthermore, Wang, Pfister and Morais (2006) explained that the tourism destination and community are related to each other. Jafari (2001) also supported the idea that tourism development do not just provide good benefits but also generate costs. The benefits that the community must gain should always depend on how much opportunity they received in tourism development.

Recent researches have established that community attitude in destination development is diverse (Gu & Wong 2006). It can be understood that, some destinations, the community identifies the tourism payback is higher than its expenditure.

The first indicator for attitude is tourism environmental impacts. According to the United Nation Environment Program (UNEP) (2015), the quality of the environment, both natural and man-made, is essential to tourism. However, tourism's relationship with the environment is complex, the article added. This involved many activities that can have

adverse environmental effects. These impacts are linked with the construction of general infrastructure such as roads and airports, tourism facilities including resorts, hotels, restaurants, shops, golf courses and marinas. The negative impacts of tourism development can gradually destroy the environmental resources on which it depends. On the other hand, tourism also has the potential to create beneficial effects on the environment by contributing to the environmental protection and conservation. This is the way to raise awareness of environmental values and it can serve as a tool to finance protection of natural areas and increase their economic importance (UNEP, 2001).

Wall and Mathieson (2006) cited that one large problem with the environmental impact has been the difficulty to measure the impacts due to its diverse, lack of baseline, lack of knowledge of cause and effect relationship and diversity of the different methods in research. A UNWTO-led report from 2008 on climate change and the role of tourism, stated that contribution to carbon dioxide emission generated mostly on transportation, accommodation and activities take an account to the contribution of these impacts (UNEP & UNWTO, 2005). However, these carbon emissions are not the sole negative environmental impact resorting from human activities, but also tourism. Other causes are land use, water use, waste, and toxics, and there are some different methods which can be used to approach the subject depending on aim and perspective.

In the study of Olga (2013), the research showed clear impacts in each of the environments observed. The biggest and the most harmful impacts were carbon emissions to the air due to the considerable amount of cars circling daily in the area. However, Olga understood that it is difficult to control such an impact. Among the other impacts were littering and damage to soil. These were negative impacts but there were positive as well aptly raising awareness about nature conservation, increasing visitors' well-being, and collecting finance that can be used for maintenance and protection.

In the study of Cavus and Tanrisevdi (2003) found that the development process controlled by the company was the primary factor in residents' negative attitudes towards tourism.

The second indicator for residents' attitude is the government management of tourism. In the context as cited by Javier (2010), supervision of the local government units also has an important role in sustainable development by having a tough control in nature's conservation. Sustainable development pertains in managing the needs of visitors and the local communities with preservation of the destination unit, in a way that it also protects the local economy, social and ecological needs. Essential to this are the role of the owners and the residents involved in the framework of destinations longevity. In this view, local authorities must take actions and be part of the execution plan to provide a safe and successful tourism development (Javier 2010).

Sharpley (2000) stated that local authorities are increasingly using the word sustainable tourism to place on their priority. With the rise of development agenda it could create jobs, community income and increase foreign exchange in the local.

Guy and Rogers (1999) supported the notion that in identifying the resident attitude survey, economic development efforts in local communities must focus on human needs to become sustainable, and seek ways to meet them, inexpensively and equitably, while protecting the environment.

Small consideration was known to examine the duties and accountability of the government in addressing destination development within the hospitality industry. Constructive dialogue for local and international strengthens the importance of the local authorities to uphold decision that can be essential for tourism development (Dinica, 2009).

A study by Brokaj (2014) stated that the awareness of possible impacts of the Vlora tourism industry is more concerned with tangible detrimental influences such as road congestion, monument degradation, and water pollution, and is less aware of the possible long-term negative impacts that tourism might have on local cultures and social issues. However, immediate plans were made by the local authorities and worked hard to have sustainable tourism. The local government pursued a one-sided approach on the strategy that promotes growth of economy, improvement of community's well-being, employment opportunity, building roads and infrastructure with concerns to the ecological effect of the surrounding.

Third indicator for residents' attitude is community satisfaction. Assante, Wen and Lottig (2012). In their study, they assessed the community for tourism in Hawaii. They try to investigate the connection in environment and satisfaction of the residents. The study revealed that the residents of the community were positively perceived that the tourism development in their area can be a good factor in destinations community satisfaction.

Finally, the last indicator in measuring the community attitude is sustainable tourism. According to Muresan, Oroian, Camelia, Harun, Arion, Felix, Porutiu, Chiciudean, Todea and Lile (2016), the idea of sustainability emerged during the past several decades are inevitability in ensuring that a well-organized destination sector based on main mechanisms: ecological, societal and economical needs of the communities concerned. To keep up a balance connecting the positive and negative impacts that the three mechanism, the other one must take into consideration the local community.

Correlation between Measures

This section discusses the relationship between the corporate social responsibility of inland resort owners and community attitude of barangay residents. The association among corporate social responsibility of the organization and community is some of the researched questions in tourism industry. The CSR implementation of the company is focused on sustainability to the community that requires attention on three independent scales namely: economic, social, and environmental sustainability Matteson and Metivier (2017). These factors are discussed to further explain their relation to community attitude.

In the study of Yusoff and Adamu (2016) about community activities of CSR showed a positive correlation between the two variables, CSR and Community. The findings is also similar with Porter and Kramer (2006) who stated that if the business wants to be sustainable, they should actively participate and engage in community activities in order to develop good rapport with the community. It was concluded that in responding to CSR activities, companies must impose considerable costs due to competitive advantage that favours good community relationship.

In parallel, Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) is the derivative of Sustainable Development (SD) that addresses corporate behavior and how environmental management strategies are used as tools for growing a company's image and cumulative effects on their environment, as well as their profits. The Triple Bottom Line (TBL) argues for businesses to measure their success according to three perspectives: people, planet and profits (Elkington, 1994). Their performance in each category represents their perceived commitment to their stakeholders, the natural environment and their economic profits, respectively.

In the same manner, resident attitude surveys assess sentiments about the impact of tourism on their community (Ahn, Lee & Shafer, 2002). Demographic data collected examines the differences within resident population groups. Residents' attitudes towards tourism are influenced by several factors. Resident attitude surveys have found that residents who value economic impacts will have favorable attitudes towards tourism but their attitudes towards environmental and cultural change are negative (Lindberg & Johnson, 1997; Walpole & Goodwin, 2001; Yoon, Gursoy & Chen, 2001).

In addition, significant relationship of the CSR has a good impact in community. Roles of CSR in community development refer to the ways the responsible behavior is perceived by community of stakeholders and how impacts are felt by them. The analysis shows that CSR proved to have many roles and the brought impacts to the community as follows: "Closer ties and interdependencies between corporations and community, sharing the costs the society has to pay due to environmental degradation, transfer of technology from international companies to developing countries, environmental protection measures that done together by corporation and the communities, poverty alleviation in the communities, human right advocacy, and helps in data gathering by ICT firms to facilitate public organization functions" (Ismail, 2009).

Based on the above related literature and studies, it can be synthesized that corporate social responsibility of a company play a crucial role in the community in support to tourism development. The involvement of the inland resort owners through involving in CSR activities promotes a good connection with the community residents. Inland resort owners should develop their good CSR practices and in order to understand and meet the needs of the community. It is also concluded that CSR is about business, government and civil society collaboration with the bottom line is the

achievement of win-win situation among the three entities. Further, the foregoing presentation and discussion of various literatures have helped in bringing into focus the two important variables of the study; corporate social responsibility and community attitude. These served as support to the results and findings of the study.

Theoretical Framework

The theory used to measure the Corporate Social Responsibility in this study was based on the triple-bottom-line concept. The study focuses on sustainable tourism that requires a company in weighing their options on the three scales: economical, societal and ecological sustainability Matteson and Metivier (2017). The idea of sustainability is the environment and should be put first into place so that continued progress in the community will take place. Putting the people or community first by placing them as valuable in the environment should be made so that sustainable development in the area will progress and will not impede the basic needs of those yet to come. In developing sustainability this study will focus on three major areas such as; economical, ecological and societal. On the other hand, the rule of sustainability can be extensively useful to many parts of our societal functions, nearly all of which can be possibly classified under one of these three areas, social, economic and environmental. The economical factor relates to the sustainability of growth and productivity, the societal factor deals with societal development and the ecological aspect focuses on the concerns of resources naturally used and protection (Dixon, 2014).

On the other hand, the Community Attitude study was based on the TIAS (attitude scale for tourism) by Lankford (2001) and SUSTAS (attitude scale for sustainability) by Choi and Sirakaya (2005). This was developed to measure the resident's attitude towards tourism and sustainability issues. In this model, the indicators include residents' beliefs, cognitions and behavioral intentions towards sustainable development. The anchored theory was also supported by the study of Ismail (2009) about CSR and its role in community development. Findings revealed that CSR proved to have many roles and delivered impacts to the community such as, environmental protection, government involvement, sustainability and community satisfaction.

Furthermore, the latter also elaborated that CSR implementation could bring a win-win situation to the three entities, namely, the business, the local government, and the local civil society, thereby conveying beneficial results to the community as business organizations properly and purposely implement CSR.

Conceptual Framework

Presented in this section is the conceptual framework of the study as shown in Figure 1. The independent variable is the Corporate Social Responsibility adopted from the triple-bottom-line theory with the three indicators which are economic, social, and environmental sustainability Matteson and Metivier (2017).

On the other hand, the Community Attitude study was based on the TIAS (attitude scale for tourism) by Lankford (2001) and SUSTAS (attitude scale for sustainability) by Choi and Sirakaya (2005). Community Attitudes has the following indicators: environmental impact which refers to the tendency of the impact of tourism on the environment implying that residents may view tourism as having either a positive or negative impact on their environment, government management on tourism which refers to the tendency of the links between the people and government, address its community's problems and concerns, enforce policies and hold influence over its communities, community satisfaction which refers to the tendency of positive factors to promote the residential community involvement in tourism destination and sustainable tourism which refers to the tendency of the commitment to make a low impact on the environment and local culture, while helping to generate future employment for local people.

Significance of the Study

This could make some inputs to the presented literature of the study. Since the tourism area has been the driving force for global workforce, economic one of the driving forces of global workforce, economical and societal well-being for the 21st century, this study is significant to future tourism researches in formulating effective studies related to CSR. As mentioned earlier in the study that CSR is a highly contested term, therefore, this study is helpful in addressing the test of implementing CSR in the community.

By formulating and executing more constructively, the inland resort owners will be able to use this knowledge in considering the community attitude of barangay residents. Moreover, the study will further benefit the community in improving its economic, social and environmental practices since the residents were major participants in the tourism development. Lastly, this study will create good linkbetween inland resort owners, the community, and the local tourism officials to foster a better implementation of CSR in Toril District.

All in all, this study helps to provide a viewpoint in tourism development. Communities will take part in endorsing the tourism industry in which can help to maintain a good working relationship between the inland resort owners and the community

Figure1. Conceptual Framework Showing the Variables of the Study

Definition of Terms

The subsequent words were defined operationally to facilitate comprehension on the readers:

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR). It is defined as an organizational concern by companies to incorporate societal and ecological concerns in the business operation and interactions with their stakeholders on intended purposes. As used on this study, this pertains to the social responsibility initiated by the owners of inland resorts around Toril area, specifically focusing on the domain of social, economic and environmental practices.

Community Attitude. In this research, it refers to the repercussion on the community thoughts and perceptions towards the different attributes brought about by tourism destinations, particularly, the inland resorts within Toril, Davao City.

II. METHOD

In this chapter, details of the methods used in the process of doing research are presented along with the explanation how the methods were chosen. The method was formulated to produce information on how to conduct the study and what would be the possible technique in getting facts. This includes the research design, research locale, population and sample, research instruments, data collection and statistical tools.

Research Design

This study used a descriptive-correlation technique and non-experimental approach. It is non experimental because the researcher examines the relationship between two or more variables which are not manipulated (Johnson, 2001). In correlational studies, a pattern or relationship can be found between variables. Both variables may increase or decrease together, or the scores of one variable tend to increase while the scores of other variable decreases (Trochim & Donnelly, 2001). Moreover the correlation technique employed endeavored to find relationships between variables, Keegan, Harwood, Spray and Lavilee (2009) pointed out that correlation can be positive or negative. This study investigated the degree of relationship between corporate social responsibility and community attitude of barangay residents.

Research Locale

The study was conducted within Toril District. Toril District is located in the third district of Davao City, Philippines. As shown in Figure 2, the city was considered densely inhabited in Mindanao because it yields a total population of 1,449,296 people as of 2010. Geographically, Davao City is the biggest city in Philippines.

For this study, Toril is the right place to conduct this research not only because there are already several existing inland resorts in the area, but also due to the fact that majority of visitors local and international tourist begin their journeys here going to other nearby localities and resorts outside Toril District. Since the area is nearby a beach and mountainous trails, many independent tour agencies and hotels are now available in this area. There are about more than 20 resorts located in this area which includes the inland resorts, beach resorts, mountain resorts and spring resorts. There are numerous inns, lodges, hostels and small hotels operated 24 hours /day so tourism businesses are increasingly growing and booming.

Population and Sample

The researcher used purposive sampling to identify and select the respondents of the study. The eligibility criterion of the respondents that has incorporated in research was found on the CSR policies implementation. This study had a total sample of 320 local respondents. To get a meaningful result, statisticians agree that the most recommended minimum sample size is 100, and

Figure2.Map of the Philippines showing Davao City

that 100 is adequate. Regression analysis provides an equation that depicts the statistical relationship between one or more predictor (Allison, 1998).

The population of this study composed the barangay residents including barangay officials of the nearby inland resort area. This includes the criteria that only respondents that are over the age of 18 were the ones allowed to be surveyed. A total of 320 survey questionnaires were distributed and retrieved from April through May 2017. On the questionnaire, respondents were asked to identify their gender, age, and primary race.

The owners of the inland resorts were not included in the selection of the respondents in order to consistently align the research extent of the CSR of inland resort owners as purely perceived by the local residents. Their close relatives were also excluded due to familiarity and to avoid biases in the selection of range in terms of CSR. Furthermore, it was done to make sure that the relevance of the study would not affect the outcome and the recommendations for further studies which may be conducted for a follow up on this research.

The selection of the respondents was also limited to those that reside near or around the location of inland resorts. As inland resorts are rapidly increasing in the district, it also brings more job opportunities to the local residents

especially to the people nearby. Because of this, it enabled to provide an impact to the community. The data below show the composition of the respondents from the selected 8 inland resorts subjected to this study.

	Name of Inland Resort	Respondents	No. of Percentage
1.	Calix Inland Resort	40	12.5%
2.	DCG Camarin Inland Resort	40	12.5%
3.	DCG Family Pool Inland Resort	40	12.5%
4.	Eden Meadows	40	12.5%
5.	Eden Nature Park and Resort	40	12.5%
6.	RLG Inland Resort	40	12.5%
7.	Villa Carmelita Inland Resort	40	12.5%
8.	Villa Nilda Garden Resort	40	12.5%
	Total	320	100%

Distribution of Respondents

Research Instrument

Two standardized instruments were utilized in this study. The first instrument measured the level of corporate social responsibility of inland resort owners and the second instrument measured the level of community attitude of the affected barangay residents of Toril.

To determine the CSR, an adapted questionnaire of Tamajón (2013) was utilized. It was tailored to go with the framework of the research and was presented to the panel of experts for validation. This instrument was used because it has reliability and validity based upon the research of Tamajon and iAulet(2013). It deals with the CSR in tourism development with indicators of social, environment and economic. The instrument was administered to selected community residents around Toril which required them to assess the CSR of inland resort owners.

Evaluating the level of CSR of inland resort owners, the following five orderable gradations with their respective range of means and descriptions were considered:

Mean Range	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very High	This indicated that the CSR of the inland resort owners are always manifested.
3.40 – 4.19	High	This indicated that the CSR of the inland resort owners are often manifested.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderate	This indicated that the CSR of the inland resort owners are sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Low	This indicated that the CSR of the inland resort owners are seldom manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	This indicated that the CSR of the inland resort owners are never manifested.

To measure the community attitude towards tourism development, the questionnaire was developed based on the Tourism Impact Attitude Scale (TIAS) this was develop t measure resident’s attitude towards tourism and

sustainability issues. In evaluating the level of community attitude, the following five orderable gradations with their respective range of means and descriptions were also considered:

Mean Range	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very High	This means that the barangay residents' community attitudes are always manifested.
3.40 – 4.19	High	This means that the barangay residents' community attitudes are often manifested.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderate	This means that the barangay residents' community attitudes are sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Low	This means that the barangay residents' community attitudes are seldom manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	This means that the barangay residents' community attitudes are never manifested.

The first draft of the research instrument was submitted to the research adviser for comments, suggestions and recommendations to improve its presentation with the corrections to be included and integrated. The final copies were submitted to the panel of experts for refinement. The final revision was made by incorporating the corrections, comments and suggestions given by the expert validators before the gathering of data. The consolidated results from the experts obtained an average weighted mean of 3.85 which has a verbal description of good. The modified questionnaires were distributed to the barangay officials and barangay residents. All inland resort tourism firms were sampled regardless of their current CSR involvement, as in previous studies. The questionnaire has undergone pilot testing and reliability test with a Cronbach alpha of .911 which means the instrument is reliable

Data Collection

Gathering of data started with the adaption of appropriate questionnaire for the topic downloaded from the internet. The items in the questionnaire were contextualized to fit the local setting and subjected to content validity by the panel of experts. Howard (2008) mentioned that in order for a questionnaire to be useful, reliable, and trustworthy, validation is important to establish the instrument that produces relevant data as standardized questionnaires provide advantages like reliability, validity, sensitivity, and specificity to the context of the study.

Upon approval of the adviser, the researcher drafted a letter of permission to conduct the study addressed to the concerned agencies and local government. After the approval has been sought from the approving agencies, the survey was immediately given to the known people of the study. The researcher personally administered the questionnaires so that if questions will be raised by the respondents, immediate explanation was made.

The instrument was administered in paper form to the respective barangay officials and residents in the nearby inland resort areas. The respondents who are 18 years old and above were permitted to join the survey. The 320 survey questionnaires were then retrieved in April through June 2017. As planned, the distribution of the respondents was at 12.5% or equivalent to 40 respondents for each of the chosen destination.

The researcher waited for the completion of each questionnaire by the respondents and ensured a complete retrieval of the instruments. Finally, the information collected was collated and appropriate statistical tools were applied in the analysis of the data.

Statistical Tools

The following statistical tools were used in the study:

Mean. This was used for the profile of the respondents and to analyze the data in the attainment of research objective one and two.

Pearson Product Moment Correlation. This method was used to resolve the significant relationship of the CSR of the inland resort owner community attitude in tourism destination.

Regression Analysis. Is the process of estimating relationship between variables; this was to test which domain of corporate social responsibility that best predicts with the community attitude.

Ethical Consideration

The researcher observed full ethical standards in the conduct of the study following the protocol assessment and standardized criteria particularly in managing the population and the data. In the conduct of the research, the barangay residents and barangay officials were given the freewill to participate without any form of consequences or penalty, therefore, the purpose and benefits of this study were described and presented to the Toril District officials.

Consequently, the rights of the respondent to contribute to the value of knowledge was considered and adhered upon. The result of the data gathered was kept private by the researcher to make sure that the confidentiality of the information will be kept classified.

Upon the distribution of the research questionnaire, the researcher ensured that the questionnaires were free from any highly technical terms allowing the respondents to easily understand the questions to be answered. Moreover, the distribution of the respondents as reflected in Table 1 showed how the population was determined. Furthermore, the data collection procedures were described as well as how the questionnaires were administered and the manner the population were involved in the study.

III. RESULT

This section shows the relationship of the CSR of inland resort owners and community attitude on barangay residents towards the local tourism industry in Toril District as identified in the study. The discussions begin with the level of corporate social responsibility of inland resort owners, the following sequence of the level of community attitude; correlation between corporate social responsibility and community attitude. Finally, the analysis and interpretation of regression of corporate social responsibility and community attitude is also presented as the final stage of analysis.

The standard deviation in two descriptive tables; Table 1 and Table 2, range from 0.68 to 0.81 are less than 1.0 as the typical standard deviation for 5-point Likert scale. This suggests that the scores in the accomplished questionnaires are close to the mean that indicates homogeneity of responses among the barangay residents in Toril District.

Level of Corporate Social Responsibility of Inland Resort Owners in Toril

Table 1 presents the responses of the residents on the level of CSR of Inland resort owners which registered an overall mean score of 3.76 or High level with a standard deviation of 0.75 indicating that majority of the items regarding the Company’s Corporate Social Responsibility is oftentimes manifested.

Table 1
Level of Corporate Social Responsibility of Inland Resort Owners

Indicator	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Social Practices	0.68	3.80	High
Environmental Practices	0.81	3.76	High
Economic Practices	0.77	3.74	High
Overall	0.75	3.76	High

Table 2
Level of Community Attitude of Barangay Residents Towards Local Tourism Industry

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Sustainable tourism	0.72	3.90	High
Government management on tourism	0.75	3.86	High
Community satisfaction	0.70	3.84	High
Tourism environmental impact	0.78	3.71	High
Overall	0.73	3.82	High

Looking the data per indicator, it can be seen that the social practices got the highest mean rating of 3.80 and a standard deviation of 0.81 with a descriptive interpretation of High; followed by environmental practices with a mean rating of 3.76 or High and a standard deviation of 0.76. Lastly, the indicator economic practices got a mean score of 3.74 or High with a standard deviation of 0.77.

Level of Community Attitude of Barangay Residents towards the Local Tourism Industry in Toril

Shown in Table 2 is the level of community attitude of barangay residents. The overall mean score of community attitude is 3.76 or High rating with a 0.75 standard deviation. The indicator, sustainable tourism got the highest mean of 3.90 and a standard deviation of 0.78 with a descriptive level of High, this was followed by government management on tourism with a mean score of 3.86 or High and a standard deviation of 0.75. Also, the indicator of community

Table 3
Correlations between Measures

Corporate Social Responsibility (Dependent Variable)	Attitude of Barangay Residents (Independent Variable)				
	Tourism Environmental Impact	Government Management on Tourism	Community Satisfaction	Sustainable Tourism	Overall
Social Practices	.553* (0.000)	.569* (0.000)	.640* (0.000)	.584* (0.000)	.586* (0.000)
Economic Practices	.542* (0.000)	.586* (0.000)	.667* (0.000)	.591* (0.000)	.573* (0.000)
Environmental Practices	.491* (0.000)	.621* (0.000)	.670* (0.000)	.559* (0.000)	.585* (0.000)
Overall	.529* (0.000)	.603* (0.000)	.644* (0.000)	.550* (0.000)	.582* (0.000)

*Significant at 0.05 significance level

Satisfaction of a mean score of 3.84 or High and a standard deviation of 0.70. Lastly, the indicator tourism environmental impact obtained the mean score of 3.71 or High with a standard deviation of 0.78.

Correlation between Measures

The relationship between the corporate responsibility of inland resort owners and the level of community attitude on community in the local tourism destination is presented in Table 3. Results revealed that the overall r-value is 0.582 with a p-value of .000. It was revealed further that the p-value of .000 is less than the level of significance 0.05. This meant that the hypothesis of no significant relationship between the level of CSR of inland resort owners and level of community attitudes on barangay residents in Toril Davao City is rejected.

The significant relationship between the corporate social responsibility of inland resort owners to community gained the r-value of .664 with the p < 0.01 lesser than the significance level of 0.05. The other indicators namely tourism environmental impact, government management of tourism, and sustainable tourism also had significant relationship to the indicators of CSR, since the r-value are .529, .603 and .550 with p < 0.01 respectively are lesser than significance level of 0.05.

Result further revealed that social practices have a significant relationship with community attitude of barangay residents with an r-value of .586 with p-value of p < 0.01. The second indicator environmental practices revealed also to have significant relationship with community attitude since it has an r-value of .573 with p < 0.01. Finally the last indicator of CSR which is the economic practices shows significant relationship with community attitude since it has an r-value of .582 with p < 0.01.

As to the relationship between each indicator, the result revealed that social practices has shown significant relationship with community satisfaction as it posted the r-value of 0.640 with p < 0.01 which is lesser than significance level 0.05. Outcome also further revealed that sustainable tourism has r-value of 0.584 and p < 0.01, government management of tourism has r-value of 0.569 and p < 0.01 and tourism environmental impact has r-value of 0.553 p < 0.01 have also shown significant relationship.

In terms of economic practices, the result shows that the indicator is significantly related to community satisfaction since the r-value is 0.667 with $p < 0.01$ is lesser than significance level 0.05. The result also further revealed sustainable tourism has r-value of 0.591 and $p < 0.01$, government management of tourism has r-value of 0.586 and $p < 0.01$, and tourism environmental impact has r-value of 0.542 and $p < 0.01$ have also shown significant relationship.

Finally, environmental practices have a significant relationship to community satisfaction, government management on tourism, sustainable tourism and tourism environmental impact as shown in the result of the study. The r-values are 0.670, 0.621, 0.559 and 0.491 and $p < 0.01$ respectively are lesser than significance level 0.05.

Regression Analysis on the Influence of Corporate Social Responsibility and Community Attitude of Barangay Residents

Presented in Table 4 is the regression analysis that revealed the indicator of corporate social responsibility of inland resort owners and the community attitude of barangay residents in Toril. The model showed that the computed f-value of 23.383 is significant at $p < 0.05$ which indicated a model fit. Also the R-squared value of 0.591 suggested that 59.1% of the variance in the community attitude was attributed to the indicators of corporate social responsibility specified in this study. This means that 40.9% of the variance could be credited to other things that are already beyond the concern of this study.

However, since the focal point of this section was the determination of the domain of CSR that best influence of community attitude of barangay resident the data show that in their singular capacities, social practices is the best predictor of community attitude. Social practices obtained a b of .248 with corresponding computed t-value of 4.355 and $p < 0.01$. Also, environmental practices obtained a b of .235 with corresponding computed t-value of 5.326 and $p < 0.01$. Lastly, economic practices obtained a b of .202 with corresponding computed t-value of 3.684 and $p < 0.01$.

The result further showed that all the indicators of corporate social responsibility of inland resort owners have significant influence in community attitude of barangay residents in Toril.

*Table 4
Regression Analysis of Corporate Social Responsibility of Inland Resort Owners and Attitude of Barangay residents*

Attitude					
	Corporate Social Responsibility (Indicators)	β	B	t	Sig.
	Social Practices	.248	.277	4.355	0.000
	Economic Practices	.202	.254	3.684	0.000
	Environmental Practices	.235	.309	5.326	0.000
R	1.769a				
R ²	.591				
F	23.383				
p	0.00				

* $p < .05$

IV. DISCUSSION

Presented in this chapter are the discussions on the data gathered and collated on the CSR and community attitude on barangay residents towards local tourism industry. The discussion starts with the community attitude of barangay residents towards local tourism industry. Also, results of correlations between measures and regression analysis on the influence of the CSR of inland resort owners on community attitude towards local tourism industry.

Corporate Social Responsibility of Inland Resort Owners

The CSR level of inland resort owners is High. Indicators with high responsive levels are social practices, economic practices and environmental practices.

One measure to check the level of CSR is social practices, which was described as high level. This signifies that the inland resort owners recognized the respect for culture in Toril area. This made the inland resort owners act equal in terms of employment opportunities in both gender. In addition, the inland resort owners also demonstrate social responsibility by equipping their facilities for the access of disabled person whenever they come to visit the resort. It also demonstrated local assistance to charity by supporting local products as often as possible. This result conforms to the study of Font (2012) which mentioned that in social practices, the interesting fact is to observe the progress regarding measures of social and economic development. All three samples claimed to support local and community development, or gender equality (most were family businesses) and to a lesser extent the promotion of work-life balance for staff. This means that the inland resort owners have the same treatment in terms of employment practices.

Moreover, this is followed by economic practices which gained a high level result. This means that the inland resorts are engaged not just in personal values and lifestyle, but more than economical causes which take part in the significant function in the community. The evaluation of economic benefits of the business such as employment of local staffs, encouraging local products and setting good salaries to employees are shown to be good by the community. This is also somehow related with the study of Knowles et al., (1999) and Stabler and Goodal(1997), which cited that company, is promoting economic practices not just to take responsibility for being sustainable but also to gain competitive advantage. Stakeholders' requirements play a part if we understand society and environment as stakeholders and not only clients, government or civil society (Sen, 2011) The last indicator of CSR which displayed a high level is environmental practices. This means that the inland resort owners are following green practices to protect the environment. The encouragement to be environmentally friendly in dealing with the nature is shown to be positive by local residents. The encouragement of using organic products, saving water and energy and renewable sources is shown also to be positive by the local people. The conservation of environment had shown a good response also. This was in conjunction to the study of Bader (2005) and Lund-Durlacher(2013) which says that to attain success in tourism destination, CSR policies of the organization should focus on the preservation of the destination's environment. This means that engaging good practices in environment, businesses can influence by these efforts and will follow the practice of locals in up keeping the environment safe. In most instances, the local people encourage other visitors to come in the area. The implementation of CSR is important because the success of every tourism destination depends on the environmental protection. This means that if the business owners engage in good preservation of the environment, the community will appreciate making them to follow the practice and encourage inviting more tourists to visit.

The statement above was supported by Ramgulan (2013) that aside from organization's involvement, the support also of community in the awareness of environmental protection is required so that there is a clear understanding to nature's preservation. Proper learning and understanding would be a guide to maintain and transform the local to behave with self-direction to secure good environmental protection.

Community Attitude of Barangay Residents towards the Local Tourism Industry

The level of attitude of barangay residents towards local tourism industry is high. Indicators with high responsive levels are impacts on environmental, local authorities' enforcement, satisfaction in community, and sustainability.

Community attitude towards local tourism industry in Toril was highly manifested particularly on sustainable tourism. Environmental impact was manifested by the majority of the barangay residents. Data revealed that the

barangay residents somehow create positive and negative effects with the on-going development of tourist spots that may affect the local setting. This causes more traffic in the area due to increased tourist arrivals, effect of water use, and the air quality of the area. This was supported in the study of UNEP (2001) which espoused the idea that the positive attributes of tourism environmental impact gives the community an adverse effect especially in the construction of roads and tourism facilities.

In the study of Cavus and Tanrisevdi (2003) found that the development process controlled by the company was the primary factor in residents' negative attitudes towards tourism. In this study, residents perceived that the costs of tourism outweigh the benefits, feelings of resentment and irritation towards tourists can develop and lower community satisfaction. Residents also believed that they have a voice in tourism planning for a more positive impact towards tourism

The outcome was supported by the concept of Muresan et al.(2016), to uphold a stability between good and bad impacts that the three cause could generate, there should take the concern in the community- the main component of development process and the most significant stakeholder. The future development and long-term planning control of the government should be in position to provide a positive impact in the community. In this case, the organization needs to analyze awareness on the impact of tourism so that this can encourage the community to create a positive way of involvement in tourism development.

Furthermore, with regards to government management on tourism, the barangay residents believed that with the intervention of government regarding the local tourism industry such as balance treatment for both community and inland resort, improvement of the public services and listening to the residents regarding their concerns on tourism impacts. This collaboration, in combination with the knowledge of residents' attitudes on related impacts, can enable more efficient use of resources to balance the demands of residents and the inland resort.

As mentioned in the related study of Javier(2011) they cited that local authorities also take part in significant function in the accomplishment of its tourism industry, as well as having a tough control in protecting its property. Sustainable development in tourism should manage of all property that gather the requests of guest and host regions while protecting the opportunities for the future, in this way the economic, social and aesthetic needs can be fulfilled.

In addition Dinica (2009) supported that local government have significant function in making the policies and implementing activities that will enable to help the local residents and inland resort owners to execute their actions towards tourism development. In this study, a constructive dialogue between the both parties is important to uphold right enforcement that is essential for tourism development.

In the same way, the community attitude of barangay residents in terms of community satisfaction was highly recognized by residents. This means that in the increase of tourism development in Toril, there possibility of raise of land prices, crowding of people and high housing development. This study has causal connection recognized by Cavus andTanrisevdi (2003) that people in the community who are part in tourism development are more affirmative towards tourism. Community contribution is necessary for tourism sustainability which can create positive reaction factor (Dyer, Sharma andCarter,2007;Ko& Stewart, 2002).

Finally, the high level for community attitude in the level of sustainable tourism was manifested by the majority of the barangay residents. Data revealed that the barangay residents are positive that the tourism development can help the community to uplift the local development. The community cited that the tourism development is important to the community. The continued expansion of tourism destination is expected to arise and long-term plan for the future development is more likely to develop, making the barangay residents access the decision making to influence future development.

This result conforms the study of Muresan et al. (2016), that the idea of sustainability are inevitability important to ensure that there is a well-organized tourism development on environment, social and economic needs of the communities concerned to maintain a balance connecting the positive and negative impacts. Thus tourism management should enlightened the needs of residents that enable tourism development to benefit from the residents while minimizing or eliminating negative impacts, particularly negative environmental impact.

Correlation between Measures

Generally, correlation between the two variables revealed a significant relationship of the CSR of inland resort owners on community attitude in barangay residents in Toril. This implied that the community attitude was influenced by the corporate social responsibility of inland resort owners. Further, it meant that manifestation of the corporate social responsibility of the inland resort owners played a significant aspect in augmenting the community attitude of barangay residents particularly both on the economic and environmental impacts.

Thus, the community perceived that the inland resort owners are caring individuals when they encouraged valuing for the way of life and the words of the community, culture and the language of the community and at the same time promoted local development that are encouraging and pleasing making them feel secure and comfortable with the tourism development in their area. Due to this positive and caring community and inland resort owners' relationship, the residents augment their interest to engage, behave and support local tourism development. Consequently, when the caring behavior of the inland resort owners is optimized, the community residing the area where the tourism destination is located is also strengthened.

The findings of this study corroborated with Yusoff and Adamu (2016) which stated that, positive correlation between the two variables, CSR and Community is important. The findings also runs similar with Rotolo and Wilson (2006) and Porter and Kramer (2006) who stated that if the business wants to be sustainable, they should actively participate and engage in community activities in order to develop good rapport with the community. They hypothesized that in responding to CSR activities, companies must impose considerable costs due to competitive advantage that favor good community relationships.

In addition, a significant relationship of the CSR must impact the community. CSR in community development refer to the ways the responsible behavior is perceived by the community of stakeholders and how impacts are felt by them. The analysis showed that CSR proved to have various roles that brought impacts to the community as follows: Closer ties and interdependencies between corporations and community; sharing the costs the society has to pay due to environmental degradation; transfer of technology from international companies to developing countries; environmental protection measures that must be done together by corporations and the communities; poverty alleviation in the communities; human rights advocacy; and, aiding in the data gathering by ICT firms to facilitate public organization functions (Ismail, 2009).

Further, the result supports with the perspective of Assante, Wen and Lottig (2012) who emphasized that creating a proposed model of TIAS is used to better recognize the community attitude towards tourism development. In the study, the result showed that the residents were somehow amplified their life status as tourism is developing. The public services are uplifted due to the arrival of local and national tourist. However, there are some issues and concerns that the residents might fear of such as the degradation of natural resources in building infrastructure development and their possibility of pollution (air, water and land). In spite of the governments' effort to ease their fear, the residents felt that the local authorities should be balance in assessing the demands of the local tourism development and implementation of the CSR practices of the organizations.

Regression Analysis of Corporate Social Responsibility and Attitude of Barangay Residents

Presented on this area is the determination of CSR and Community Attitude of barangay residents thru the use of Regression Analysis. The predictors of corporate social responsibility were social practices, economic practices and environmental practices. Among the predictors of attitude are tourism environmental impact, government management on tourism, community satisfaction and sustainable tourism. This implies that the inland resort owners should strengthen and intensify the corporate social responsibility of the organization.

Result of the study showed a significant influence of the domains of corporate social responsibility of inland resort owners on the attitude of barangay residents as mentioned in the correlation section of this study. This means that when the corporate social responsibility of inland resort owners is high, the community is also satisfied. This study also exposed 59% of the CSR of inland resort owners significantly influence community attitude another 39 percent were influenced by other attributes which are not part of the study. The results of the study, therefore, supported the research of Chandralal(2010) which suggested that there is a positive insight and a positive outlook toward the tourism

development of the community. The residents expect that tourism will boost more and additional guest will come in the local setting in the long run.

V. Conclusion

Based on the results of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

It has been determined that the social, economic, and environmental impacts are the domains of corporate social responsibility that best influenced the community attitude of barangay residents in Toril on tourism development in their respective areas. Likewise, between these three domains, the social impact is the best predictor in its singular capacity.

Furthermore, the overall level of corporate social responsibility of inland resort owners was high. Its indicators revealed the following results: high for social practices, high for economic practices and high for environmental practices. On the other hand, the overall level of community attitude of barangay residents was also high. Its indicators revealed the following results: high for tourism environmental impact, high for government management on tourism, also high for both community satisfaction and for sustainable tourism. Unarguably, research hypothesize that there is a significant relationship between the CSR of inland resort owners and community attitude of barangay residents in Toril as described.

The overall corporate social responsibility of inland resort owners significantly influences the community attitude of barangay residents in Toril. In their singular capacities, social, economic and environmental practices can significantly influence the community attitude of respondent barangay residents in Toril. To sum it up, this present study has confirmed the proposition of Porter and Krammer (2006) who stated that if the business wants to be sustainable, they should actively participate and engage in community activities in order to develop good rapport with the community. That in responding to CSR activities, companies must impose considerable costs due to competitive advantage that favors good community relationship.

VI. Recommendation

In the pursuit of determining the specific domain of CSR on inland resort owners" and community attitude towards local tourism industry in Toril, and upon considering the results of this study, the researcher came up with the following recommendations:

The result which underscores this study is that a high level in social, economic and environment significantly influence the community attitude. The researcher therefore suggests that inland resort owners should be discreet in its dealings with the surrounding community and in sincerely addressing their concerns and be sensitive to the needs and the wellness of the community they are operating in order to raise their ratings of this study higher. This implies that inland resort owners, assisted with the government authorities, should incorporate activities focus on how to appropriately deal with the community's concern regarding the tourism development in the local area.

Pursuing the above recommendation, the inland resort owners may deliver more effort to encourage the community to attend and participate in their engagements to the community as initiated either by the local government and the inland resort owners to hold constructive dialogues and round-the-table talks especially on the issues affecting local employment, community services and support, and protecting and preserving the environment - more particularly, perhaps, on rehabilitation, maintenance, or preservation of nature which are mutually beneficial to all concerned in a win-win situation.

Additionally, the study found out a significant relationship between corporate social responsibility of inland resort owners and community attitude of barangay residents in Toril, thus, inland resort owners must be consistent in showcasing their CSR activities to the community so that residents can perceive holistic environment integral to the local tourism development.

In the same manner, it is recommended that conducting CSR programs should be done regularly and consistently, so that the community residents are given the opportunity to engage beneficial undertakings that the

tourism development has brought in their respective localities under the monitoring of the local government units in order for them to appreciate the inland resort extension activity to the community. This activity can certainly promote positive relationships that can boost local tourism development for the good of all stakeholders.

Finally, further research related to this study may also be conducted on a wider scale and on a greater population in order to fully and precisely identify the greater domain of corporate social responsibility that would elicit a more positive correlation between the attitude of the barangay residents and the inland resort owners for both to be more communally benefited, mutually cohesive, and economically uplifted.

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